

Nationalism education in elementary school: A systematic literature review

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ABSTRACT

This article aims to present a literature review on nationalism education in Elementary School in the latest literature because there are still few who research it. This research applies the systematic review literature method with the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analysis (PRISMA) protocol. The research stages include identification, screening, eligibility, inclusion, and analysis presentation utilizing the help of the Publish or Perish 7 application, VOSviewer, and NVIVO 12 Plus. The results of searching for articles according to the theme in Scopus through the Publish or Perish 7 application there are 226 articles which are filtered into 50 selected papers. The topic findings are character education, education, architectural education, democratic parenting, nationalism attitude, character building, international education, digital citizenship, acculturation, literacy, citizenship education, traditional games, national education, de-colonialism, ethnicity, implementation of character education reinforcements, ethno-nationalism, and curriculum. The research findings mention that nationalism education in elementary schools is a conscious effort of educational institutions to instill students' understanding, knowledge, and attitudes to love and defend the country implemented through civics, social studies, and character education, which has an impact on character building, students' love for language, culture and the integrity of the country. Future research needs to examine nationalism education in elementary schools according to approaches, strategies, media, materials, technological developments, and research trends.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Indicators of national development success in each country are based on several studies mentioned through the successful implementation of nationalism education in elementary schools [1]–[5]. The purpose of nationalism education in China is to build and maintain the nation's unity and form of national identity [6]. Studies in Southeast America call nationalism learning aimed at shaping the character of nationalism and patriotism because it gets less attention [7]. Critical geopolitical studies, critical terrorism studies, educational geography, and youth geography in 12 countries (Turkey, India, Nigeria, Sri Lanka, Peru, Spain, Kenya, Russia, China, Egypt, the Philippines, and Papua Guinea) recommend strengthening nationalism education in schools. This proves that the teaching of nationalism is urgently applied [8].

Studies in several countries recommend strengthening nationalism education [9]–[13]. The cause of the erosion of nationalism is due to the factors of radicalism and theory [12], [14], [15], online learning

during the COVID-19 pandemic [16], globalization, and technology, which requires strengthening the character of nationalism in education [17], [18]. Nationalism education enhances the spirit of maintaining the integrity of the country and preventing the emergence of terrorist movements because most terrorists are those who do not have nationalism [19], [20]. The urgency of strengthening nationalism education in elementary school is caused by the rise of the movement to lower nationalism and the revolutionary movement to separate from the nation [21], extremism, radicalism, and terrorism in education [22], [23]. As an educational institution, elementary school plays a role in transforming the nation's ideology. Elementary students must be instilled with the values of nationalism, national ideology, concepts of nationality, skills, and a sense of responsibility towards their country [24], [25]. Nationalism education in schools is carried out through learning in and outside the classroom, such as local cultural habituation, literacy, scouting, and others [26], [27].

Character education is the nation's investment to prepare future generations who love their country [28]. One such character is nationalism, a basic understanding to build the spirit of citizenship and defend the nation from colonization and bullying that must be instilled early on in elementary school [29]. Nationalism education is an effort to build a sense of pride to be part of the country and nation that impacts the idea of producing something to make the nation reputable. Therefore, nationalism education is needed to form a good attitude and personality to build a government [30].

Nationalism education is carried out through the value clarification technique (VCT) with the stage of identifying, assessing, and making decisions on life problems that impact pride in the nation [31]. Nationalism learning as part of nationalism education in elementary school is applied through a holistic curriculum, intra-curricular, extra-curricular programs [32], local wisdom of a nation [33], multicultural learning [34], habituation of school culture in elementary school [35], novel learning [36], hero role models who have elements of transparency, sense of social responsibility, and courage to defend the country [37]. Education and learning nationalism for students must use a scientific approach and adjust the development of the industrial revolution era 4.0 [38], [39].

It is important to study research on nationalism education in elementary school. This is because national development in a country is determined by the success and failure of teaching in elementary school to build nationalism in students [40]–[42]. Nationalism education must be technically transformed into learning through various curriculum designs, model innovations, and learning methods that are appropriate for the times [43], [44]. Few studies related to nationalism education in primary schools explore the concept, technical implementation, and impact on students in detail. This article offers the idea, learning, and impact of learning nationalism in elementary schools based on recent research [45]–[50].

Using the systematic literature review method, this background tries to dig up descriptions of articles related to nationalism education in elementary school. The results of this study are expected to produce a report on the concept of nationalism education in elementary school. Researchers raise the central question: How is the current literature about nationalism education in elementary school? Thus, the specific question of the study: i) How is the nationalism education concept in elementary school?; ii) How is the implementation of national education in elementary schools in several countries?; iii) How does the impact of learning nationalism on elementary school students?

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Research design

The research design here uses the systematic literature review (SLR) method, which is a method to determine, identify, and evaluate research in a structured manner to find answers to research questions formulated by researchers [51]. The SLR method in this article explores the concept of nationalism education in elementary school. The research began with identifying articles relevant to nationalism education in elementary school on the Scopus database. The SLR in this article refers to the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analysis (PRISMA) technique [52]. This study identifies nationalism education in elementary school in recent articles in the Scopus database. The four stages carried out by researchers are identification, screening, feasibility, and inclusion [53], [54].

2.2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria for selection of publications

In the inclusion and exclusion stage, the researcher makes his criteria for entering articles in this research [55]. First, the pieces that are searched are only those indexed by Scopus. Second, the search for articles in the Scopus database is assisted by the Publish or Perish 7 application. Third, articles are published in journals from 2018 to 2022. Fourth, the pieces are searched based on their suitability with the theme and research topic. Fifth, reports are limited to only those published in scientific journals and English.

2.3. Screening and eligibility assessment for data analysis

The findings of the article on the Scopus database are filtered as needed. Relevant articles are included, and irrelevant ones are not used. Article filtering is tailored to titles, abstracts, and keywords. The same theme was discarded, after which 50 selected papers were entered into the Mendeley application and saved in research information systems (RIS) format; the next step was entered into the VOSviewer application to map the initial network of theme linkages. Strengthening the relevant research arguments requires an initial analysis of thematic associations of the articles used in this study through the VOSviewer application. The initial analysis of thematic associations in Figure 1 shows that nationalism education in elementary school has a very complex association pattern.

Figure 1 shows the discussion and study related to elementary school nationalism education are very close to several other study themes, such as nationalism education in elementary school and the impact of learning nationalism. However, the aspect of online learning has far from the piece of nationalism education studies, such as the theme of character education, education, architectural education, democratic parenting, nationalism attitude, character building, international education, digital citizenship, acculturation, literacy, citizenship education, traditional games, national education, de-colonialism, ethnic, implementation of character education reinforced, ethnonationalism, curriculum, and others.

Figure 1. Initial network visualization

2.4. PRISMA flow diagram

The selected articles are obtained from the screening and eligibility assessment for data analysis stages. The themes it is read in their entirety from title to conclusion. After that, the report is entered into the NVivo 12 Plus application for analysis, and the results are presented according to the research questions asked [56]. The details are inferred from the search process using the Prisma flow diagram as in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Flowchart of search and screening process [57], [58]

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the findings in the Scopus database, there are 226 articles according to keywords. The details are the keyword “Nationalism Education in Elementary School” there are six their reports, the keyword “Nationalism Education” there are 200 articles, the keyword “Nationalism Education in Basic Education” there four pieces, the keyword “Nationalism in Elementary School” there are 11 articles. The keyword “Nationalism Character in Elementary School” there are five articles. The same article was discarded and 50 papers were selected. Before presenting the qualitative results according to the research questions, it is necessary to deliver the article findings first. The presentation is based on the year of publication, journals (journal name, volume, edition, year), methodology, country, and relevance to the research questions (RQ), namely nationalism education concept in elementary school (RQ 1), the implementation of national education in elementary schools in several countries (RQ 2), and the impact of learning nationalism for elementary school students (RQ 3). The findings can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Mapping results of 50 articles based on links to research questions

No	Methodology	Country	RQ
1	Qualitative and quantitative method [59]	Netherlands	RQ 1
2	Analysis Study [60]	China	RQ 2
3	Qualitative [61]	Belgium	RQ 2
4	A systematic procedure for reviewing or evaluating documents [62]	Vietnam	RQ 3
5	Qualitative descriptive [63]	Indonesia	RQ 3
6	Qualitative descriptive [64]	United States	RQ 1
7	Qualitative descriptive [65]	Sweden and USA	RQ 3
8	Qualitative approach [66]	Indonesia and Japan	RQ 1
9	Quantitative and qualitative methods [67]	Indonesia and Malaysia	RQ 3
10	Qualitative approach [68]	China	RQ 1
11	Qualitative study [69]	Indonesia	RQ 3
12	Descriptive-analytic method [70]	Indonesia	RQ 1
13	Instruments development [71]	Indonesia	RQ 2
14	Mixed methods approach [72]	Hong Kong	RQ 1
15	Qualitative study [73]	Iceland and Finland	RQ 1
16	Research and Development [74]	Indonesia	RQ 3
17	Comparative (quasi-experimental approach) [75]	Indonesia	RQ 2
18	Qualitative method (content analysis) [76]	Hong Kong	RQ 2
19	Analyze the historical development [77]	France	RQ 2
20	Qualitative descriptive research [78]	Indonesia	RQ 1
21	Qualitative study [79]	England, Germany, France, and USA	RQ 1
22	Qualitative (empirical analysis) [80]	USA	RQ 1
23	Comparative research [81]	Scotland	RQ 1
24	Qualitative and comparative study [82]	Syria and Iraq	RQ 1
25	Qualitative descriptive approach [83]	Indonesia	RQ 3
26	Qualitative (Analysis) [84]	America and Philippines	RQ 3
27	Quantitative (self-reported questionnaire) [85]	Italian	RQ 3
28	Quantitative research [86]	Indonesia	RQ 2
29	Positivistic/quantitative approach [87]	Indonesia	RQ 3
30	Case study (empirically) [88]	China	RQ 3
31	A quantitative study using survey design [89]	Malaysia	RQ 3
32	In-depth analysis [90]	Israel	RQ 2
33	Qualitative approach [91]	Indonesia	RQ 2
34	Qualitative descriptive [92]	Bangkok, Thailand	RQ 3
35	Qualitative Method (Historical Review) [93]	Indonesia	RQ 2
36	Qualitative descriptive [94]	Indonesia	RQ 1
37	Qualitative research method [95]	Indonesia	RQ 3
38	Investigative Research [96]	Syrian and Turkey	RQ 1
39	Empirical study (survey and administration) [97]	Taiwan	RQ 3
40	Analytical Research [98]	Japan	RQ 2
41	Qualitative approach [99]	Indonesia	RQ 2
42	Qualitative descriptive [100]	Canada	RQ 2
43	Quasi-experimental research [101]	Indonesia	RQ 1
44	Hermeneutic approach [102]	Indonesia	RQ 1
45	Mixed method (quantitative and qualitative) [103]	Indonesia	RQ 3
46	A Systematic Literature Review [104]	China	RQ 2
47	Analysis method, systematic investigation (purposive and snowballing) [105]	Nigeria	RQ 3
48	Qualitative (ethnographic approach) [106]	Indonesia	RQ 2
49	Quantitative approach [107]	Indonesia	RQ 1
50	Quantitative method [108]	Thailand	RQ 1

3.1. Nationalism education concept in elementary school

Nationalism is a form of patriotism. The manifestation of nationalism is the belief and understanding of national priorities, the desire to dominate the international community, and emphasizing that the interests of one's country are more important than other nations [72]. The concept of nationalism education in Iceland and Finland refers to the methodology of nationalism, which is essentially a theoretical idea in the humanities and social sciences to generate a spirit of love for the nation [73]. Nationalism education for elementary school students in the USA is largely a more flexible notion of citizenship, emphasizing patriotism and the virtue of defending one's country [64]. Nationalism education is a generalization of the concepts of citizenship and nationalization to form the character of loyalty, obedience to the constitution and law, respect for differences in social groups, and recognition of equality before national law [79]. Nationalism, in a study in Iowa City, Iowa, USA, is referred to as a cultural conception and movement to defend national culture and identity [80].

For the Netherlands, nationalism is a necessity for industrialized societies. They need a trans local normalization and a uniform hegemony of science. In this context, the education of the concept of nationalism was adopted long ago and taught through civic education in public schools [59]. Research in Scotland says nationalism is inseparable from education, as it teaches a sense of belonging to the nation and country [81]. In historical records, the concept and revival of Chinese nationalism were brought by missionaries in the 1930s through religious learning and nationalism education in children aimed at forming the indigenization of the Chinese people and weapons against global secularization [68].

Nationalism education in Indonesia is a conscious effort to shape the character of elementary school students based on Pancasila or Indonesian five principles to maintain the integrity of the nation. The feeling of nationalism manifests in commendable behavior toward humans, nature, and God [66]. In Indonesia, nationalism is an understanding, strength, and social capital that a single perspective cannot explain. Nationalism can be seen from aspects of culture, thought, residence, modernization, politics, gender discourse, religious movements, ethnicity, linguistic constructions, and modern national movements to maintain the nation's integrity [70]. Nationalism education in Indonesia has become an effective government program through strengthening character education (PPK). Nationalism is the main character in the PPK program that is strengthened for elementary school students, including the characteristics of gotong royong, independence, integrity, and religion [78]. Nationalism in Indonesia is a character education intended to make students knowledgeable, faithful, and responsible. Aspects of nationalism education include knowledge, feelings, and actions by the norms of a country [107].

The source of nationalism values in Indonesia is the motto "Bhinneka Tunggal Ika". It contains the importance of religion, cooperation, compassion, intelligence, courage, and willingness to sacrifice for global diversity, which is the central axis of nationalism education [102]. Nationalism education in Indonesia unites and sustains the spirit of nationalism, culture, religion, and art. Nationalism is an attitude to see the nation as a whole from the aspects of its identity, religion, culture, and art that are incorporated into the curriculum [94]. The concept of nationalism education in Rojava, Syria, and Kurdistan Region, Iraq, in the form of ideology and vision of the state, national movement, and politics incorporated into school textbooks [82]. Studies in Syrian and Turkish say nationalism is the absolute loyalty of every citizen to the state territorially. Nationalism is manifested in patriotism, the implementation of the message of history, and the culture of the nation [96]. Nationalism education teaches goodness to learners to become honest citizens [101]. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization's (UNESCO) 2015 citizenship study mentions that nationalism education that builds student character consists of three elements. The first is cognitive. The indication is knowing, thinking, and analytically about local, national and international wisdom. Second, socio-emotional. The indicators are that students value unity, respect differences, have humanitarian empathy, and are responsible. The third is action. On the hand, students are responsible for the local community, nation, and state for peace and sustainability [108].

3.2. The implementation of national education in elementary schools in several countries

Nationalism education in China is conducted to promote the country's ideology, return to local morals, and build national consciousness to defend the country [60]. Nationalism education at the elementary, junior, and high school levels in Belgium is implemented through civic education, which can be diffused into history, social science, law, and literature materials [61]. Nationalism materials in Hong Kong are developed through a philosophy of education, multicultural education, identity, civics, and citizenship education [76].

Nationalism education in Indonesia is applied to several subjects, including history. Historical material strengthens character, knowledge, values, and attitudes related to the country's image, building scientific, critical reasoning, and awareness of state defense [86]. Nationalism education in Jakarta, Indonesia, is conducted through spatial understanding, religious awareness, economic awareness, cultural awareness, and organizational awareness models [69]. Research in Indonesia suggests that nationalism

learning is done through character and civic education. This research recommends the urgency of innovation in the aspects of learning materials, models, methods, and media to make nationalism education more attractive to students [99].

A 2019 study in Indonesian elementary schools found that learning nationalism was effective with the learning media “*Wayang Pahlawan*” and documentary films that successfully increased students’ nationalism. However, the documentary film in this research was most effective in fostering nationalism than the “*Wayang Pahlawan*” learning media [75]. Moderate Islamic education is the implementation of the concept of nationalism in education. Children are taught national and Islamic values such as unity, respect for differences, cooperation, tolerance, and others [93].

Nationalism education in Indonesia is carried out through the integration of moderate Islamic education and involves Islamic mass organizations. Strengthening average Islamic values such as tolerant, reasonable, and fairness can increase the spirit of nationalism through the attitudes and behavior of students [91]. Indonesia also implements nationalism education through habituation techniques, role modeling, conditioning the school situation, integrating learning with nationalism topics, and extracurricular activities [106]. The implementation of nationalism and nationality education is carried out through learning innovations in the form of Accountability, Nationalism, Public Ethics, Anti-Corruption (ANEKA), and Tri Hita Karana (THK), which are oriented toward building a spirit of love for the country [71]. Nationalism learning in France integrates the national education system through applying scientific and modern approaches to the Bible, incorporating Catechism learning, and integrating religion with the nation’s schools to become a school for all [77]. Nationalism education in Israel is implemented through textbooks that apply the ethnonational model of nation-states to shape learners’ commitment to the values of democracy, tolerance, and protection of minority rights [90]. Nationalism education in Japan is taught to elementary school students through textbooks, stories, and metaphors portraying the struggle to defend their nation [98].

Nationalism education in Canada is implemented by strengthening national insight through two methods. First is applying the concept of “prism metaphor,” where educational institutions in Canada familiarize the power of internationalization in education. Second, the idea of tipping points describes domestic and international forces in uniting and encouraging academic actors to have the same knowledge and attitudes as the government [100]. Nationalism education in research in China is implemented through water sprinkling festival, *naadam* festival, torch festival, preservation of heritage and social identity, and lessons through Chinese textbooks [104].

3.3. Impact of nationalism learning on elementary school students

The mainstreaming of nationalism in education in Vietnam has resulted in massive improvements to the national education system, meeting schooling demands (modernization and industrialization), and improving educational institutions’ management by removing authoritarian bureaucracy [62]. Studies in Europe (Sweden) and North America (USA) stated that the performance of nationalism education has a contradictory impact, educating students to live with complexity. The implementation of nationalism education there ensures that democracy, synonymous with school reform in the USA, should be promoted. Still, now support for anti-democratic governance is also growing [65].

Nationalism education fosters a sense of nationalism, unity, and integrity. This is because studies in schools in Jayapura Regency, Indonesia, show that there is still a separatist movement and a desire to separate from Indonesia [63]. Nationalism education in primary schools in Indonesia has an impact on the beliefs, attitudes, and habits of singing the Indonesia Raya song, proudly speaking Indonesian, maintaining the good name of the nation, willing to sacrifice for the country, and keeping the flag flying in border areas that are still prone to conflict [67]. Nationalism education in Indonesia strengthens the religious character of students. They practice religious tolerance towards followers of other religions, living in harmony without disputing. Nationalism education strengthens religious symbols, not the other way around [74]. Nationalism education taught in primary schools in Indonesia through the subjects of Civics and Pancasila strengthens the preservation of local wisdom values and the preservation of culture [83]. Supporting nationalism in education and learning in South Tangerang City schools, Banten, Indonesia, impacts the attitude of rejecting radicalism and extremism of teachers and students. Of the 147 respondents, 65.4% experienced an increased sense of patriotism and readiness to fight radicalism, while 73% of students became moderate and tolerant [103].

Research in the US and Philippines suggests that nationalism education positively affects the retention of English as the language of the union. English becomes a frame of nationhood, conveying modernity, national unity, and national progress. This is because linguistic concepts are interconnected with a sense of national pride [84]. Nationalism education taught in Italian schools has an impact on strengthening the values of democracy, respect, loyalty to national unity, respect for the symbols of the nation-state, and national identity [85]. Nationalism education has a severely impacts on students’ attitude, concern, and courage in maintaining their nation’s sovereignty. Nationalism is a total capital for the state to maintain its

existence and power. Nationalism contains the strength, vitality, and inspiration to maintain, preserve, and raise the country [87]. Strengthening nationalism in China through the film “Wolf Warrior II” as a learning medium has an impact on the birth of comprehensive strength and the realization of ideological orientation on a domestic and global scale towards the Chinese Nation [88].

Nationalism education in Malaysia impacts teachers and learners in mastering digital literacy because the nation’s awareness today is determined by the understanding of digital citizens through the education process [89]. Nationalism education in Bangkok, Thailand, has had an impact on strengthening a more nationalist Thai curriculum. The reason is that before the teachers there seriously taught nationalism, the nationalism curriculum adopted was still a mixture of the western curriculum, which was considered more established and modern but unsuitable for local conditions in Thailand [92]. A study of 110 teachers in Taiwan found that using traditional music to instill nationalism in students positively impacted teachers’ and students’ love of Taiwanese indigenous music over western music [97].

Nationalism education through civic learning has an impact on the characters of students. The first is the application of human rights principles. Second is the appreciation of the value of courtesy. Third, being responsible in social activities, and fourth, respecting the roles, responsibilities, and rights of others. Fifth is a critical, independent citizen in community activities [95]. The condition of COVID-19 is disrupting education. This is even more chaotic when citizens do not have nationalism because it impacts dishonesty, corruption, and the unaccountability of the state budget. Strengthening nationalism education is essential because it affects the character of the nation’s children [105].

4. CONCLUSION

Findings in the current literature inform that nationalism education in primary schools is a conscious effort made by educational institutions to instill understanding, knowledge, and attitudes toward students to love and defend their nation and country. Nationalism education in primary schools is implemented through civics subjects, social sciences and humanities, literature, character education, models, innovative learning media, and others. Nationalism learning in primary schools has a positive impact on improving the education system, state management, ensuring the integrity of the state, building the character of the nation’s children, love for language, culture, and symbols of the state, and the integrity of the country. Future researchers must explore nationalism education in primary schools according to different approaches, strategies, media, materials, technological developments, and emerging research trends.

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